

Training Activities Schedule

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Technical References

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- ¹
- PU = Public
 - PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 - RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
 - CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

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Summary

Summary of Deliverable 9.3

Deliverable 9.3 provides an update on the proposed training schedule within the INN-PRESSME project. Training activities will be carried out to promote the new knowledge generated during the project and the ecosystem operational scope as well as to create new links with interested audiences.

The INN-PRESSME *training activities* are facilitating informal and formal discussions across the industry and business community by gathering key market players, industry associations, clusters, and services and technology providers.

They will focus on a topic of broad interest with presentations by leading experts, that will foster the generation of innovative concepts.

The proposed training activities and materials are adapted to the end-users needs and to the test cases, to fit sectors requirements.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and objectives

The deliverable details the proposed schedule of the training activities to be carried out in the framework of the project. **Five e-learning modules** will be broadcast through the E-Learning Platform and **four webinars** will be implemented. In addition to attract the critical audience, a set of training manuals, guidelines and other documents will be developed and prepared, along with the creation of video and photo databases. The INN-PRESSME E-Learning Handbook focusing on test cases, will be prepared to target the end-users of the exploitable technical results of the project: SMEs, large companies, civil society, scientific community, industry associations, clusters, related Open Innovation Test Beds, and policy makers

The main outcome of this deliverable is to provide the consortium a first proposition on the training schedule, especially to partners that will be directly involved in the implementation of training activities for the full life-cycle of the INN-PRESSME.

1.2 Structure of the Deliverable

Deliverable 9.3 is defined in five main chapters:

1. **Training schedule:** based on the preliminary agreement between INN-PRESSME partners conducting training in the project.
2. **The various IT platforms to be used for the webinar trainings:** the most popular and practical webinar platforms are introduced.
3. **E-Learning Guidebook and additional resources to conduct the training activities:** a general description of the training materials to be developed in the project.
4. **INN-PRESSME E-Learning Platform:** the E-Learning Platform to be developed is described within more details.
5. **National training events and clustering workshops in local languages:** the French community will be addressed by IPC through dedicated workshops dealing with the open calls
6. **Dissemination of the training activities and materials**

1.3 Methodology

The deliverable was prepared prior to an extensive arrangement between IPC, G!E and GEO. The timing of the training events was preliminarily set with the key project partners who will conducting the trainings as presenter or moderator (VTT, STAM, CEA, CIDETEC and FRAUNHOFER- ICT).

1.4 Relation with other activities and deliverables of the project

This deliverable is linked to other outputs of work package 9, for example one outcome of the training activities could impact the clustering activities through the implementation of national webinars in local language reusing the webinars' content and outcomes. The clustering workshops will also help to attract additional audience to the upcoming webinars and to the E-Learning platform.

Table 1 Deliverables of the project related with D9.3

Deliverable number	Deliverable name	Delivery month
D9.4	Clustering activities with the OITB ecosystem	M48
D9.6	Report on clustering activities with EC initiatives	M48
D9.9	Report on the training activities including training material	M48

2 Preliminary INN-PRESSME training schedule

At the time of submission of Deliverable 9.3 (June 2022), the project partners agreed on the following training schedule of the INN-PRESSME project:

- **Webinar 1 on open calls is proposed to be held in November 2022.** The main topic of the webinar will be focusing on the presentation of the Open Call and the description of the OITB services. Results from the pilot lines will be presented, with the description of the portfolio of potential offers and the capitalisation options of the demo case. The webinar will be led by STAM, backed by VTT, CEA and it will be supported by additional Service Providers. The expected duration of the first webinar is supposed to be set between 1,5 and 2 hours.
- **Webinar 2 on the open calls is scheduled for May 2023.** The audience will receive an updated presentation about the Open Call and the description of the OITB services. The first Open Call results will be summarised, for example the number of proposals received, the ones that were accepted, and the status of first experiments. More feedback will be given to participants with offering a Q&A session. The change of rules

from feedbacks and the addressed market will be explained, by showing the services and offering the open calls to support the projects. The webinar will be led by STAM, and supported by VTT and CIDETEC. The expected duration of the second webinar is supposed to be set between 1,5 and 2 hours.

- **The third webinar on the SEP offer is planned to be held in April 2024**, where the global offer of the SEP will be shown, as well as the legal structure, without the Open Call. The offer will be the same, but it will not be advertised as a free service anymore. The spotlight will be on the sectoral demo cases, for example packaging and energy. The webinar will be led by STAM, backed by WP and test case leaders VTT, CIDETEC and FRAUNHOFER-ICT and IPC, depending on the sectors and demo case leaders. The expected duration of the third webinar is supposed to be set between 1,5 and 2 hours.
- **The final webinar is suggested to be organised in September 2024** with the main topic on transport and consumer goods. The presenters will be showing the products and description of the SEP and how it will contribute to projects. Demonstration of the offer in the use cases will be also presented. The webinar will be led by WP5 and 6 leaders: CIDETEC and FRAUNHOFER-ICT, helped by STAM, depending of the sectors/demo case leader. The expected duration of the fourth webinar is supposed to be set between 1,5 and 2 hours.

Additional external leading experts will be invited to speak at these webinars, to propose new perspectives and tackle current issues around circular economy, industrial solutions for biomaterials and novel bio-based materials.

The preparation of the E-Learning module content will be completely depending on the availability of the training materials developed within the various INN-PRESSME work packages, however a preliminary schedule was also drafted in this deliverable:

- **E-Learning content 1 (by March 2023)** - Technologies to produce novel nanomaterials and biobased materials (mechanical, chemical, biotechnology and thermochemical means). The average duration to proceed with the first E-Learning content is between 30 and 60 minutes. The first E-learning content will be provided by pilot line owners: VTT (PL1 and 7), RISE (PL2), Polymarix (PL3), IWN (PL4) and Gnanomat (PL6).

- **E-Learning content 2 (by October 2023)** - Technologies of dispersion coatings and printings and the most important process controls and characterization methods for the materials. The average duration to proceed with the second E-Learning content is between 30 and 60 minutes. The second E-learning content will be provided by VTT (PL14), Fraunhofer-ISC (PL10), CEA (PL13) and Cidetec (PL5 and 12)
- **E-Learning content 3 (by January 2024)** - Technologies of thermoplastic coating and 3D printing technologies and the most important process controls and characterization methods for the materials. The average duration to proceed with the third E-Learning content is expected between 30 and 60 minutes. The third E-learning content will be provided by IPC (PL9 and 15), CEA (PL8), Fraunhofer ICT (PL11) and AIT (PL16).
- **E-Learning content 4 (by April 2024)** - Eco-design/Sustainability, nano-safety, recycling and reuse as material. The average duration to proceed with the fourth E-Learning content is expected between 30 and 60 minutes. The fourth E-learning content will be provided by IRES, AIMPLAS, KCL and CEA.
- **E-Learning content 5 (by November 2024)** - Regulations, standardization, patent, landscape, IP. The average duration to proceed with the last E-Learning content is expected between 30 and 60 minutes. The fifth E-Learning content will be provided by AIMPLAS, UNE and SDP.

Along the webinar, participants will be able to raise their hands and ask questions after each presentation or after the full webinar session (this option will be decided later on). The audience will also be given the opportunity to ask questions in written in the chat box.

For quality management purposes, after each webinar event, the participants will be asked to rate the webinar presentations with feedbacks in the form of short surveys or questionnaires.

It should be noted that the above dates can be considered only preliminary and the actually delivered webinars and E-Learning events dates / durations might be different from the ones in this deliverable, according to the special conditions of the project.

3 Proposed IT platforms to be used for the INN-PRESSME webinars

3.1 GoToMeeting

GoToMeetings is an online meeting, desktop sharing, and video conferencing software package that enables the user to meet with other computer users, clients or colleagues via the internet in real time. It is designed to broadcast the desktop view of a host computer to a group of computers connected to the host through the Internet. Transmissions are protected with high-security encryption and optional passwords. By combining a web-hosted subscription service with software installed on the host computer, transmissions can be passed through highly restrictive firewalls.

Figure 1 - GoToMeeting screenshot (Source: <https://support.goto.com/meeting/new-attendee-guide>)

3.2 Microsoft Teams

Microsoft Teams is a proprietary business communication platform developed by Microsoft, as part of the Microsoft 365 family of products. Teams offers workspace chat and videoconferencing, file storage, and application integration.

Figure 2 - Microsoft Teams screenshot (Source: <https://techcommunity.microsoft.com/t5/microsoft-teams-blog/what-s-new-in-microsoft-teams-may-2019/ba-p/658941>)

3.3 Zoom Meetings

Zoom enables quick adoption with meeting capabilities that make it easy to start, join, and collaborate across any device. Zoom Meetings are able to sync with participants calendar system and to deliver streamlined enterprise-grade video conferencing from desktop, mobile device. Zoom's robust security settings ensure disruption-free meetings.

Figure 3 – Zoom Meeting screenshot (Source: <https://explore.zoom.us/en/products/meetings/>)

In the coming months of the project, consortium partners will discuss and agree which online platform could be the most suitable for the purposes of delivering the INN-PRESSME webinars. The decision will be depending on the size of the expected audience, GDPR issues and the practicalities of the webinar platform to be used.

4 INN-PRESSME E-Learning Guidebook and additional training resources

Geonardo will develop the INN-PRESSME E-Learning Guidebook that will be supporting online participants; it will facilitate participation of additional stakeholders, thus widening the outreach of the INN-PRESSME information exchange tools. Geonardo being the sole producer of the platform has the intention to continue the to exploit the platform after the end of the project, in close collaboration with Greenovate! Europe, ESCI and other INN-PRESSME partners involved in the development of the training contents. The training materials for both the webinars and E-Learning module content will be developed by the related technical partner in the project.

5 INN-PRESSME E-Learning Platform

5.1 Objectives

Overall, the INN-PRESSME E-Learning platform will have the following objectives:

- To increase the capacity building of stakeholders involved in activities related to OITB;
- To maximise learning, offering theoretical guidance as well as opportunities for interactivity and learn-by-doing;
- To provide a reference point for stakeholders involved in the training activities, acting as a repository of training materials and other available support materials;
- To provide opportunities for local stakeholders to network and share knowledge and experiences with each other.

5.2 Technical specifications

The E-Learning module is expected to be based on LearnDash (<https://www.learndash.com/>) plugins (Course Grid, LMS and ProPanel). The project website's existing theme will be applied on the plugin. After a successful registration, users will become Members and can access the E-Learning section. Users associated to the Partner role will be also able to access to the Member Area. Ask the tutor feature will be implemented as a contact form. The Forum plugin (<https://bbpress.org/>) will be added that Members can use.

5.2.1 Announcement Board

On the Announcement Board of the E-Learning Platform, the first page users will visit, they will be able to see:

- A short description of the INN-PRESSME E-Learning Platform: the course content and other relevant pages
- Announcements by the project partners on the uploading of new materials and documents, upcoming training sessions, updated FAQs, or any further useful piece of news.

5.2.2 Registration

Access to all E-Learning content will be completely free, but registration will allow Geonardo and all other partners to better monitor the appeal and visibility of the platform, as well as to

smoothly evaluate its content and technical performance. Should few individuals only register initially, a more consistent promotional campaign will be launched. Registration to the E-Learning platform will be very simple. From the Announcement Board, users will be able to easily access the registration page. After filling out all fields, users will receive an automatic e-mail that will allow them to quickly finalise the process.

5.2.3 E-Learning Course Modules

The approximate content of the E-Learning modules had already been defined (see section 2), however the exact titles of the INN-PRESSME E-Learning Modules will be worked out later on in the project, based on the decision of the trainer participants and the potential needs that might arise from end-users during the performance of training sessions. Each Module can be further divided into Chapters. These will contain video presentations with an English narration and a final exercise.

Concerning the Chapters' content, a good option is to create interactive and meaningful training material using Storyline 360 (<https://articulate.com/360/storyline>). The following examples show how training material can be transformed into interactive E-Learning:

- **Simple presentation slide with animation.** This template can be used to introduce new subjects and present information. The course will contain audio narration in order make it engaging and user-friendly. While talking, the narrator will be visually supported by pictures, animations, keywords or infographics. As it is not necessary that the user reads all content, only part of the script will be visualised, for example keywords or definitions. A script will be made available for download.
- **Presentation slide with video.** Videos may be added, such as tutorials on how to use the INN-PRESSME solutions or a piece of informative video such as interview, testimonial and so on.
- **Context based multiple choice exercise.** Based on previous explanations and presentations, the user is given a task to perform by clicking on the right "hotspot" in the software screenshot. The user receives immediate feedback on the choice, and this allows to quickly learn the main functions of the software and to put knowledge into practice.

5.2.4 Forum (optional)

This page will facilitate networking and knowledge sharing amongst the platform users. They will be able to ask questions to each other, exchange useful tips and questions to each other. Geonardo will act as supervisor of the forum together with the support of the technical experts of the different INN-PRESSME partners for what it concerns the management of specific topics within the forum discussion. In order to do so, point of contact will be provided to technical experts with an administrator access to the E-Learning platform.

5.2.5 Document repository

On this page, users will be able to easily download relevant documents, for example:

- INN-PRESSME best practices
- Public documents from other ongoing projects and initiatives with objectives similar to INN-PRESSME;
- Links to relevant YouTube videos
- Other interesting links.

5.2.6 Ask the tutor (optional)

A contact form will be made available for users to directly contact project experts, for specific questions they may have related to the INN-PRESSME results, their local needs they may have. In order to fasten and facilitate quality replies to the questions, various roles could be assigned for questions related to the topic of the OITB. Users will be able to choose the relevant category for their question, and an automatic e-mail will be sent to the relevant partner.

5.2.7 Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

A Frequently Asked Questions page will allow users to quickly find a solution to their questions. Based on the most common and relevant questions received during the online training sessions, this page will be continuously updated during the whole duration of the project. Whenever this page is updated, an announcement will be added to the Announcement Board.

5.3 Support to training sessions

The Platform will support online training sessions in the following ways:

- Announcing the date and link of upcoming sessions on the Announcement Board and via automatic e-mails to all registered users;

- Providing further reference and review possibility to face-to-face participants (downloadable documents, updated content, etc.);
- Providing updates to the FAQ page according to questions and issues emerged from those sessions.

5.4 Feedback collection and analysis

In order to fix potential technical bugs of the E-Learning Platform and to maintain relevance of the training material on the platform, Geonardo will collect feedback from all registered users via a simple online questionnaire that will appear at the end of the session (the compilation of these questionnaire will be compulsory before ending the session). The survey will be based on sentences, on which users will be able to provide their agreement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 stands for „I fully disagree” and 5 for „I fully agree”. The feedback form will be fully anonymised and will potentially contain the following questions:

Feedback on the technical aspects of the E-Learning platform

1. The registration process was smooth.
2. The interface of the E-Learning platform was user-friendly and clear.
3. Navigation on the platform was easy.
4. I was able to properly follow all content’s display.
5. I could always access the Forum and contribute to it.

Feedback on the E-Learning content

1. The INN-PRESSME E-Learning Module met my expectations and needs.
2. The INN-PRESSME E-Learning Module content was relevant and meaningful.
3. The INN-PRESSME E-Learning Module content was consistent with the overall training approach.
4. The length of this INN-PRESSME E-Learning Module was appropriate.
5. My overall experience was positive.

6 Other INN-PRESSME webinars and additional national training events in local languages

SDP will organise an internal IP webinar about the use of the most important tools on how to protect the generated results in INN-PRESSME.

Webinar 1 will be translated into French and broadcast by IPC among its community. This additional webinar is proposed to be held in December 2022.

7 Dissemination of the training activities and materials

To ensure best practices and knowledge are shared with as many stakeholders as possible, the webinars, the e-learning modules and the Handbook will be:

- Widely disseminated (both through targeted emails to key business stakeholders and via the INN-PRESSME and the partners' social media channels)
- Open to everyone interested
- Recorded and made available online and at no cost

The slides of these webinars will be shared with all registered participants. The INN-PRESSME partners will have the opportunity to translate the materials into local language and use it as a training tool within their business networks. The INN-PRESSME Consortium will also be able to disseminate the webinars and materials through their own networks. ESCI, GEONARDO and G!E will activate their European and national media contacts to promote the training activities and reach more impacts.

8 Conclusion

This deliverable summarises the preparatory work that was made by IPC, G!E and Geonardo in order to define the basic requirements and initial planning of the schedule to the training activities within INN-PRESSME. The first training activities in the form of webinar are expected to start in November 2022 and will conclude with the last training event in September 2024. The INN-PRESSME partners dedicated themselves to the realisation and delivery of the training sessions and active participation of the webinar with quality presentations and discussions, while Geonardo will provide the IT infrastructure and web-programming resources.

